

Wereldoorlog I kraterlandschap bij Ieper (België)

The Conference Brussels 4-5th December 2013 has been a very interesting meeting with a lot of useful discussions. CAA-NL-FL would like to thank the organisation at the Flemish Heritage Agency (www.onroenderfgoed.be), and all participants.

Check out the themes, programme and presentations below!

Themes

- Innovative approaches of digital media in surveys and excavations (remote sensing, digital on-site registration, etc.).

The amount of available digital data, as well as the possibilities of the use of digital media in surveys and excavations, has increased enormously in the last decade. This theme will focus on novel digital approaches for survey and excavation, for example high resolution (ground-based and airborne) remote sensing, 3D registration of archaeological excavations, and digital site registration systems (high resolution GPS systems, tablet computers, etc.). Papers can deal with the use of specific techniques, or on the set-up of systems for capturing and integrating data from a multitude of such practices.

- Standards and best practices for managing digital archives (databases, spatial data, etc.);

The 'boom' of digital media also has a significant 'dark side'. A multitude of approaches, software, and file formats are used for capturing, storing and managing digital data. Existing international norms and standards are often neglected. In the longer term this will lead to a huge amount of fully or partly inaccessible data. The focus of this theme is on good practices for storing and managing large amounts of digital data from archaeological excavations and surveys, and the use of (international) standards and open source applications.

- The use of digital media in the research of war heritage.

With the 100 year anniversary of the start of World War I in sight, the attention for its archaeological heritage has increased in Flanders over the last couple of years. The extent, nature and diversity of this heritage (trench lines, dug-outs) requires both a landscape scale approach, as well as detailed site investigations. Archaeology can also be aided through the use and analysis of historical sources, such as aerial photographs and 'trench maps'. In this theme we aim to bring together examples of interdisciplinary surveys of WWI heritage, including spatial analysis of historical sources, the use of remote sensing techniques, etc.

Programme

4 December 2013, thema prospectie

12.30: Ontvangst en registratie

13.00: Welkomstwoord en introductie

13.15: John Nicholls: Geophysical surveys on the de Kommel plateau, Dilsen Stokkem, Limburg

13.45: Joep Orbons: Archeologisch-geofysisch onderzoek, zoek de verschillen. Waarom werken geofysische onderzoeken soms wel, soms niet?

14.15: Toni Schiemanck: "ArchaeoCopter": Recording Archaeology with Low-cost UAV and SfM

14.45: Ivan Kisjes: Archaeological experiments with a low-cost quadcopter

15.15: Pauze

15.30: Jo Van Valckenborgh, Nancy Van Camp, Toon Petermans: A new Lidar survey for Flanders – a promising tool for discovering our cultural heritage.

16:00: Erwin Meylemans: DHM Vlaanderen I en II en archeologie in Vlaanderen, een terug- en vooruitblik.

16.30: Vragenronde en discussie, synthese

17.00: Einde

5 december 2013, thema's registratie en archivering/WOI

9.00: Ontvangst en registratie

9.30: Rens De Hond & Maurice De Kleijn: Mapping the Via Appia in 4D (Work in progress)

10.00: Jeroen De Reu, Wim De Clercq, Pieter Laloo: Image-based 3D modelling, a(n) (r)evolution in archaeological excavation practice?

10.30: Wouter De Maeyer & Bart Cherretté: 'De evolutie van een analoog naar een digitaal registratiesysteem. Mogelijkheden voor een meer optimale archivering en ontsluiting?'

11.00: Koffiepauze

11.15: Henk Vanstappen: Het geheugen van de architect: een reality check

11.45: Discussie en vragen

12.00: lunch

13.00: Maurice de Kleijn: Testaccio, A Digital Cultural Biography App

13.30: Ann Degraeve: ARCHES – Archaeological Resources in Cultural Heritage, a European Standard

14.00: Tijs De Schacht & Lien Lombaert: Safely deposited. Can standards for registration bridge the gap between field and storage practice? A look at collections registered by means of erfgoedinzicht.be

14.30: Hilde Verboven: het WO I erfgoed in Vlaanderen: een introductie

14.40: Birger Stichelbaut: In Flanders Earth: WW1 aerial photographs in a museum context

15.10: koffiepauze

15.25: Wouter Gheyle, Yannick Van Hollebeeke, Ignace Bourgeois, Jean Bourgeois, Rebekka Dossche, Veerle Van Eetvelde, Stephanie Verplaetse, Birger Stichelbaut: De herontdekking van lang vergeten oorlogslandschappen. WO I-luchtfotografie en terreininventarisatie in de provincies Antwerpen en Henegouwen

15.55: Timothy Saey, Marc Van Meirvenne Marc, Birger Stichelbaut: Multi-signal geophysical survey of WW 1 battlefields near Ypres

16.25: Vragenronde en discussie, synthese

16.55: Algemene ledenvergadering CAA Nederland Vlaanderen

17.25: Einde